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**Study program: Language studies for
intercultural communication**

MA PROJECT

**A comparative study on entrepreneurship in regards to
self-efficacy, gender, and culture/ social norms
between Western, Asian, and Arabic cultures**

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Abstract

The environment of entrepreneurship consists of a social and cultural frame that affects entrepreneurship activities. This paper selected important factors impacting these activities and analyzed the mediating effect of self-efficacy, gender, and culture and their relationship within entrepreneurship, to investigate differences between some Asian, Arabic, and Western cultures.

Design: partial structural table of the following rates: Fear of Failure, Perceived Capabilities, Female/Male early-stage Entrepreneurship activity, and Female/Male Opportunity driven early-stage Entrepreneurship activity in addition to the environmental framework, Cultural and Social Norms. The data selected are from the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor. This consortium provides statistics about different entrepreneurial indicators organized by countries according to the available years.

Findings: My study focused on one cognitive factor (self-efficacy), one environmental factor (culture), and one biological factor (gender). It proved correlations between indicators and presented gaps and differences between cultures, as well as similarities. Although my findings have proven correlations between the factors listed above, there was not enough evidence to prove that culture is the mediator of the relationship between gender and self-efficacy, nor gender to be the mediator of the relationship between culture and self-efficacy.

Implications: the results are important for the progress of researching entrepreneurship behavior across cultures in regard to self-efficacy and gender.

Originality: Cross-cultural comparative studies of gender, self-efficacy, and social norms are quite rare and there is a big call for research in this area.

I did not utilize the traditionally used regression analysis methods, I focused on visual representations and humanistic explanations.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, self-efficacy, gender, culture, social norms, fear of failure, perceived capabilities

1. Introduction

Entrepreneurship aims to create something new in the world as a response to a discovered or created demand. An innovative idea is often considered to be valuable because the entrepreneur takes certain risks in order to pursue this idea. The path is full of uncertainty while exploiting profitable business opportunities. Researchers pivoted their attention from the opportunities to the factors that push entrepreneurs to make such business decisions. They started investigating behaviors and beliefs that affect an individual's entrepreneurship intentions, and they also started to notice the impact of cultural norms that surround the entrepreneurs' environment.

Because society directly reflects on the entrepreneur's social education, it plays a certain role in shaping his or her behaviors. To be able to offer a new business, the entrepreneur needs to evaluate the market which would need a deep understanding, as well as the society's norms. An individual entrepreneurship intention is affected by current entrepreneurship actions. Those actions go through a cognitive process in which the entrepreneurs not only evaluate the entrepreneurship environment but also the confidence in the opportunity. Self-assessment is a crucial part of this process, if not a decisive one for starting the business.

Entrepreneurship provides many advantages to the country. This is why it is important to conduct research on important aspects of entrepreneurship, it is a major element in fostering the development of a certain nation.

The context of my papers is the USA, Germany, South Korea, China, Morocco, and Saudi Arabia. These countries will enable a comparative analysis to reflect upon differences and similarities. However, we don't know if the culture of each country boosts entrepreneurship action, or perhaps cultures impact

entrepreneurial actions by activating entrepreneurial gaps like gender differences

in pursuing different opportunities or activates the level of confidence and self-efficacy of individuals who might pursue entrepreneurship, thus many unresolved behavioral and environmental factors that could impact one's ability to engage in entrepreneurial actions. Certainly, the outcome of this research, according to the research question in the next chapters, would have an important contribution to public policymaking in the countries under investigation.

In this paper, I analyze entrepreneurship from different perspectives, such as self-efficacy, culture, and gender. I argue which culture encourages entrepreneurship activities the most, I bring to the fore the differences between selected countries, and also make the correlations between the indicators: fear of failure, perceived capabilities, female/male early-stage entrepreneurship activity, female/ male Opportunity-Driven early-stage entrepreneurship activity, and cultural and social norms.

The structure of the paper is as follows: first, I will discuss kinds of literature on self-efficacy, culture, and gender. Second, I compile the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor data from 6 countries which allows me to differentiate 3 categories of cultures. Third I make two comparative analyses, one at the category level and one at the country level Finding correlations between indicators is to disprove the crimping recognition of gender contribution, self-assessment, and different cultures.

2. Literature review

Entrepreneurs create jobs and contribute to economic development and innovation, and it is known that women choose entrepreneurship due to economic problems, and being affected by cultural beliefs about gender, which present many barriers. Especially with increasing industrialization, the issue of women's family responsibilities (childcare) becomes more important. Women still have the major responsibility for families and children across many countries. In this literature review, I tried to offer a context for the relevance of such a topic by providing some research done using the database: the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) statistics which I adapted to my descriptive and comparative analysis.

Cross-cultural studies are virtually limited even though these studies are important to researching the relationship between culture, gender, and self-efficacy in regard to entrepreneurship (Mueller and Conway Dato-on 2011). In their paper, the authors quoted Minniti *et al* (2005) and Mueller (2004) to emphasize the gaps between men and women when it comes to motivation, desire, and intention to become an entrepreneur. Recent studies linked these gaps to cultural and national differences by using the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor 2007 report across 41 countries. The surveys suggest that men have better self-perception than women across cultures mostly due to stereotypes attributed to women in so many cultures and societies. Citing (Williams and Best 1982; Wood and Eagly 2002) business is considered only for men, as a masculine field. Matching up to this point, women think they have fewer skills required for business (Wilson *et al* 2007).

There are many comparative studies done using the GEM database to explain the gap between genders in entrepreneurial activities. However, up to 2007, these GEM studies did not isolate the impact of culture on the gap and tackle the correlation between culture and the gender gap.

Geert Hofstede was mentioned in a lot of articles I cited in the references because of his work on IBM employees in fifty countries. From his large-scale study, we can understand that self-efficacy is related to behavioral aspects, which, in turn, are related to culture. To understand this connection, we need to go through the dimensions of culture.

Citing Shane (1993) in their paper, Hechavarria and Reynolds (2009) proved the significant effect of culture on innovation. In their study, they applied Hofstede's dimensions (Hayton et al. 2002), of which the key dimensions to analyze national culture are: individualism-collectivism, uncertainty avoidance, power distance, and masculinity-femininity, to conclude at the end that "cultures with high individualism, low uncertainty avoidance, low power distance, and high masculinity are ideal foundations for entrepreneurial endeavors that value innovativeness" (Hechavarria and Reynolds, 2009, section4)

Emami and Khajeheian (2018) worked on highlighting the relationship between social norms and entrepreneurial actions. Social norms can be dictated by shame and guilt that affect behavior in the first place; by default, they affect self-efficacy toward entrepreneurship. The two scholars defined self-efficacy as the belief in the capability to execute/perform entrepreneurship tasks. They cited Krueger et al (2000) who argued that high self-efficacy leads to stronger entrepreneurship behavior. To demonstrate the connection between social norms and self-efficacy, Iran's culture has been employed as an example, being a conservative country that relies on family connections and favors. This aspect gives this culture a group orientation (collectivism, in Hofstede's terms).

Esnard-Flavius (2010) explained that Hofstede's High masculinity value in a country means that the gender gap in entrepreneurship is bigger than the gap in countries with Low masculinity value. Analyzing African culture, she mentioned Lisowska (2002) who put the spotlight on religious, social, and historical

stereotypical beliefs when it comes to comparing men and women. These beliefs,

Thus, hinder women entrepreneurs and make their path harder. The result would be a low level of women's self-efficacy, as well as low competencies in their entrepreneurial domains. On the other hand, Boyd and Vozikis (1994) suggest that if the opposite occurs, i.e., if women are encouraged, the future of entrepreneurship will be brighter for them.

If we review the research done about North Africa in detail, including Morocco and Tunisia, which have growing Manufacturing trades, outstandingly in Materials and Pieces of clothing production, and have had some accomplishments in expanding women's interest in the paid private part then as opposed to the defeminization seen in Egypt, Morocco, and Tunisia, we find they have had some accomplishment in expanding women's participation in Entrepreneurship. Most other MENA nations, in any case, have been less effective because of their more internal-looking exchange approaches. The cases of Morocco and Tunisia demonstrate that women's growing access to the work market can be accomplished at first by advancing the development of segments that have generally been available to female interest, for example, textiles and garment manufacturing. As for Morocco, research shows that women in female-headed households are 37 percent more likely to be economically active than women in male-headed households. Because of social norms, society puts much pressure on women and ties them to household duties; accordingly, women are valued for their investment in their families. Moreover, men and women in Morocco experience much more different work showcases advance. Concerning labor mobility, men outperform women backed up by the analysis of employment transitions over the period 2007-2007. Although the Feminization of the Moroccan private sector started in 1990 in textile and garment manufacturing, Economic activities experience gender segregation that may change with progress and development; however, it will always persist because it is too deeply rooted. It is all affected by gender-biased rules and regulations which leads to unequal business

positioning.

There are specific cultural aspects of Moroccan society that can explain these gaps. To go further in the details in entrepreneurship, for example, the average age of women entrepreneurs is 40, most of them are married and have children, 2 of 3 have a university degree, and have almost 9 years in business. These elements may reflect on the self-efficacy and self-assessment indicators.

The perceived idea within society is that men should be more concerned about achievement and career success, in addition to having a certain expected behavior, like being competitive and tough (Hofstede & Hofstede, 2005, p. 117). On the other hand, women should be concerned about the household, childcare, and so on. Such perception is expected to present barriers for women entrepreneurs. Hechavarria et Reynolds (2009) inferred, from the previous work of (Krueger 2000; Carsrud and Krueger 1995; Krueger and Carsrud 1993), three critical perceptions of entrepreneurship intention: entrepreneurship activities are perceived as Personally desired, Supported by social norms, and Feasible. Socio-cultural characteristics have an important role in business creation (Hechavarria et Reynolds, 2009). Moreover, Social norms are important depending on how society and culture support entrepreneurship (Carsrud *et al* 2006).

Although the work of Salfiya Ummah and Haleem (2021) was initially a comparison among two categories of Muslim women, it shows the effect of the culture of a country on the entrepreneurship intentions of these women. In Sri Lanka, Muslim women are more confident and they don't rely on the help of the government or non-governmental sources to start their own businesses. Then they explained the situation of women being confined in the house most of the time instead of getting the proper training for entrepreneurial activities. These cultural factors could negatively affect the confidence of women and their intention towards entrepreneurship instead of being the source of support they can get to enhance their business performance.

One of the reasons I chose the topic is that not so many studies examine the relationship between entrepreneurial self-efficacy and gender. Chronologically speaking, the progress of women in a male-dominated environment made the entrepreneurial self-efficacy differences between genders diminish. Mueller & Conway Dato-on (2011) (citing Reynolds *et al.* 2004) pointed out that Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) shows that the differences in entrepreneurship activities among countries and the gender gap are more significant in low-income countries as compared to high-income ones.

The lack of support from the social environment has been a huge barrier; however, sometimes it has a positive effect as it creates determination among women. It is known that men have more social support, noting that they are being relieved from child care and household chores, as they make spouses support them in business without pay. Women succeeding in entrepreneurship are perceived as nontraditional. For this reason, most women who started businesses have modest objectives regarding business. Comparing American to Asian cultural environments, the lack of entrepreneurial support for women is higher in CHINA than in the US.

Theoretically speaking; ESE¹ is affected by the national Culture depending on the role modeling that can limit or endorse ESE for both genders. “International comparative studies of ESE are extremely rare.” (Mueller et Conway Dato-on 2011, p17)

Taking an example of an industry, Lang et Liu (2022) focused on the fashion field by analyzing the previous work of McGee *et al.* (2009) to test entrepreneurship self-efficacy's impact on the level of business performance. This study highlights the lack of studies based on this domain of industry.

Apart from Hofstede, Bandura was also mentioned in most of the articles reviewed, Bandura (2001) stressed the historical records concluding that in

1; Entrepreneurial self-efficiency

With regards to careers that are *historically* seen as non-traditional for women, females have a significantly lower level of self-efficacy.

Regardless of what history taught us about nontraditional fields for women, Esnard-Flavius (2010) concluded that the perception of Entrepreneurship self-efficacy greatly affects the *Entrepreneurial Attitude Orientation*. As for Moos et Visser (2021), they connected self-efficacy with the belief of succeeding according to McGee *et al.*'s (2009:966) definition. Hence, whether it's personal or within an organization, self-efficacy measurement is an essential measurement to determine the future of an entrepreneur.

What Moss and Visser (2021) tried to do is to determine whether gender differences influence the level of entrepreneurship self-efficacy and whether culture and gender could explain why some individuals are "more prone" to become entrepreneurs. Cultural beliefs about gender and entrepreneurship definitely affect the self-assessment of both genders. Moreover, to a large extent to which such assessment affects the existence of Business startups in an account of the gender gap.

Research among genders states that women are stricter with themselves and assess themselves as less able than similarly situated men. Men are about twice as likely as women to pursue entrepreneurship. Gender stereotypes and beliefs can affect women's judgment in assessing themselves. Self-assessment results of manipulating relevant human, financial, and social resources are different among genders and create a plus to the existing gap leading to having more men entrepreneurs than women. Gender segregation can be both pull and push factors; apart from that, women have less access to information and other crucial resources. Even in developed countries like the Europe ones and the USA, women still report that they assign themselves a lack of credibility because of their gender. Men are always perceived as more valuable; stereotypes always consider

them as individuals who “count” (Ridgeway and Correll 2004). When

women perform well, their performances are inconsistent with status-based expectations, described as a double standard: women are stricter with themselves in receiving feedback and they try to score higher (Foschi, 2008). These beliefs affect task performance; researchers found that male high school students made higher assessments of their competence at math than female students did, despite having the same actual math ability.

Around seventy-five percent of both male and female business people begin organizations to seek a chance (as opposed to out of need); yet, men show progressively constructive discernments about circumstances and their capacities, just as lower dread of disappointment.

Self-efficacy can be analyzed on two levels. The first one is through the *Fear of failure* level: fear of failure is one of the critical aspects that affect people's progress and intentions towards entrepreneurship. As per a recent report on Fear and enterprises, Fear is a noteworthy mental boundary to most business pioneers, as it can keep them from going out on a limb for their prosperity.

Since women's contribution in this field is negatively perceived by societies due to the level of resistance to change and discrimination among genders, Women have higher fear of failure rate than men in correlation with the economic factors. This observation is more apparent in China's data compared to the USA's.

The second level on which self-efficacy can be analyzed is the competency level. Lack of competency was identified more among female entrepreneurs. Again, this is observed more in China in comparison to the USA. Thus, young Chinese women perceive self-employment as a way to reduce their traditional dependence on male family members and gain control over their income. For women in Turkish and Spanish societies, lack of experience seems to be the most important barrier to entrepreneurship progress. However, for women in the United States, fear of

Failure and lack of competency are considered to be more important barriers than for men in the same countries. According to the GEM data, women think they have half the entrepreneurship ability of men. They consider themselves less capable. As a result, it is assumed that gender has no moderating effect on the relationship between the perceived fear of failure and the entrepreneurial intention in the USA and China. A case example: lack of confidence in front of the committee can result in more hurdles in convincing bankers of the woman's creditworthiness, hence hindering, generally, the process of accessing capital. Self-confidence has a crucial role here, it creates the necessary skills to succeed in a business, it is also important in determining the level of interest in young people (Kickul *et al.*, 2004) and it consequently impacts teenage girls' choices positively or negatively.

Research on career interest among teens revealed that girls have less interest in entrepreneurship than boys. These research studies proved a direct relationship between entrepreneurial intention and self-efficacy (Kickul *et al.* 2004). Raising the issue of the comparison of the level of self-efficacy among men and women, it is demonstrated that it is lower for females than for males in mid-school, high school, and adult early career life. Researchers have demonstrated a significant difference in self-efficacy among teenage girls (a particular demographic category) of different racial backgrounds and ethnicities. This factor pushes the aspiration of young girls to become entrepreneurs in the future. Moreover, the White/Caucasian students were overrepresented Wilson *et al* (2007). Self-efficacy is usually high in upper-range socio-economic levels. According to Steinbugler, Press, and Dias (2006), racial and gender stereotypes affect black women and reflect on others' attitudes toward them in the business field. Mueller *et Conway Dato-on* (2011) divided the countries into three categories to determine the effect of culture; and conducted a study on a group of students to determine the impact of gender as well, comparing males and females within two-country samples. The apparent stereotype is that entrepreneurship is a

masculine field. However, one of the interesting findings of that research is that

This particular stereotype is fading with time. In the USA, the more years pass by the weaker this perceived idea becomes. Esnard-Flavius (2010) contributed to this research topic with some particularities. In her research, male students reported some typical feminine qualities expressing their need for a secure, stable, and risk-free environment.

Experience has a critical role in increasing self-efficacy. Experience is the part that gives the real sense of what it takes to have a successful business. Standard decisions and policy-making are mostly formed through analyzing male experience, as a consequence female entrepreneurs are judged by parameters that don't apply to them. This cultural infrastructure, behavioral barriers, and other factors contribute to hindering female progress and production in the entrepreneurial world. Females are obliged to adapt themselves to norms abstracted from male-dominated experiences, which makes everyone search for qualities seen to be limited in females' contribution. All the sectors are embedded with discrimination, especially gender discrimination. This pushes women, the marginalized party, to seek self-employment, and this results in a lack of experience before resorting to self-employment in the first place. As a result, lack of experience in the entrepreneurship world became associated with the female gender without considering the factors involved. For that reason, we can notice a difference in the length and type of experience between men and women.

Noreña-Chavez and Guevara (2020) confirmed the strong relationship between entrepreneurial self-efficacy and innovative behavior, based on the work of Dalborg and Wincent (2015), demonstrating the positive relationship between them. Moreover, self-efficacy controls motivation, effort, perseverance, emotional stability, and stress levels. This explanation is inferred from Bandura and Locke's (2003) theory. Noreña-Chavez and Guevarra compared the two genders: First women have lower entrepreneurial self-efficacy compared to men (Wilson et al. 2009, mentioned in Noreña-Chavez & Guevara, 2020: 354)) Second, women have

less entrepreneurial experience impacting self-efficacy (Henry et al. 2017 quoted

in Noreña-Chavez & Guevara, 2020: 354)) Third, women with a higher level of entrepreneurial self-efficacy are more likely to generate their own business (Tegtmeier et al., 2016 quoted in Noreña-Chavez & Guevara, 2020: 354)). The level of business performance reveals this strong relationship.

Campo (2011) made an analysis of self-efficacy on entrepreneurial intentions, specifically entrepreneurial self-efficacy (the ability to successfully start a new business). Contrary to the previously gathered research, Campo (2011), in agreement with Zhao et al (2005), rejected the positive relationship between entrepreneurial self-efficacy and gender, although it is related to entrepreneurship intention, as women reported lower intentions to become entrepreneurs. Campo's research concluded that there is no difference between men and women regarding both entrepreneurial self-efficacy and entrepreneurial intentions.

3. Methodology

The purpose of my study is to shed some light on the theoretical premises of entrepreneurial self-efficacy and to extend the cultural application to three different geo-cultural categories. Given the above, this study capitalized on the data from the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM). In the following section, the details of the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor are discussed. The data selection, the study's measures, and the target population are also explained.

According to the official website (www.gemconsortium.org), GEM was created to emphasize the importance of entrepreneurship in the world. As such, entrepreneurship creates employment as it promotes innovation and productivity. It also points out society's challenges, such as the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) or the economic shockwave created by the COVID-19/Coronavirus pandemic. GEM contributed greatly to the values of entrepreneurship. This could be illustrated by an example worth mentioning: in 2008, policymakers used GEM's research on how to recover from the Great Recession. GEM mainly carries out survey-based research on entrepreneurship and its ecosystems worldwide. It is also a great network consortium and the only global resource that creates this type of data using its unique tools, claiming to be the largest ongoing study in the field. GEM uses two complementary tools - the Adult Population Survey (APS) and the National Expert Survey (NES). Along with policymakers and entrepreneurs, academics benefit from GEM's data using a unique methodology technique allowing them to establish longitudinal analyses. To date, more than 300 academic research studies have made use of GEM.

International organizations use GEM's indicators on their official website. For this reason, I consider it credible as it generates its data with the help of 500 specialists. Plus, more than 200.000 interviews with experts were conducted

annually.

Legally speaking, the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor is a limited company without share capital, registered as the “Global Entrepreneurship Research Association”. National teams are the national sponsors, and each team is led by a local university or academic institution reporting annually about their findings. According to Minniti, Bygrave & Autio (2006), this database started as a project including 10 participating countries, launched in 1999. With time, the number of participating countries increased until reaching 115 economies. Now, GEM is a big database that contains large cross-cultural data, organized according to many behavioral and environmental factors and issues. In simple words, it is a pioneer of a sample composed of adults of 18 years old minimum. The data is generated periodically, every calendar year from each participating country that goes through an Adult Population Survey (APS), and then 2000 randomly selected respondents will answer some behavioral questions related to entrepreneurship (Klyver & Thornton, 2010). There is a slight difference in the way the data is generated from one country to another. Even though this database is culturally heterogeneous it has an overrepresentation of wealthy countries.

GEM measures Entrepreneurial Behavior and Attitudes indicators through APS, from which I chose four indicators. To reflect on self-efficacy, I am working with the "Perceived Capabilities" Rate, which represents the percentage of the eighteen to sixty-four-year-old population excluding those involved in any entrepreneurship stage, who believe they have the required skills and knowledge to start a business. This explains whether or not they believe in their abilities. The second indicator is the "Fear of Failure" Rate, which represents the percentage of the population between the ages of eighteen and sixty-four excluding those involved in any entrepreneurship stage, who indicate that fear of failure would prevent them from setting up a business and this explains the way they assess themselves. Furthermore, to reflect on gender differences, I am working on the following two indicators: Female/Male early-stage Total Entrepreneurship Activities

Ratio which is the percentage of the female population between the ages of

eighteen and sixty-four who are either nascent entrepreneurs or owners-managers of a new business, divided by the equivalent percentage for their male counterparts. The last indicator is the Female/Male Opportunity-Driven TEA Ratio, which represents the percentage of those females involved in TEA who claim to be driven by opportunity since they don't have other job options and who indicate that the main driver towards entrepreneurship is being independent or acquiring more money divided by the equivalent percentage for their male counterparts.

Moreover, thirty-six experts in each participating country administer the National Expert Survey (NES) to collect data on the context in which entrepreneurship takes place in a country according to nine **Entrepreneurial Framework Conditions (EFCs)** that enhance (or hinder) new business creation in a given country. Among these conditions I am working on just one, The **Cultural and Social Norms**, which explains to what extent social and cultural norms encourage or enable new entrepreneurship methods or activities.

Hypothesis 1: there is a difference in the way entrepreneurship is encouraged in various parts of the world

RQ1: Is the Western culture more or less encouraging than the Eastern one (Asian & Arab)?

Hypothesis 2: Eastern cultures have higher gender gaps than Western ones.

RQ2: what may cause the gender gap in the opportunity-driven TEA in the countries under investigation?

Hypothesis 3: there is a correlation between the type of culture, self-efficacy, and gender.

RQ3: which cultures affect self-efficacy positively and which do not?

RQ4: which cultures affect female involvement positively?

RQ5: what correlation is there between the three (culture, gender, and self-efficacy)?

RQ6: Is there any difference between these variables under the geographical areas under investigation? (Within the category and between categories)

In the following, I am going to compare the statistics of three categories of cultures: Western, Arabic, and Asian Cultures. First, I am going to explain why I have grouped them in the way that will be seen below. Second, I am going to make a comparison within each group. Third, I am going to compare the three categories on a global scale. Finally, I am going to draw some conclusions.

4. Descriptive statistics

4.1. First category: Western culture

The first category contains the United States and Germany. The reasons why I chose these two countries as a representation of Western culture are as follows: Both are developed countries that belong to the high-income group. They have similar standards of living, religions (the most popular is Christianity), and human rights perceptions. The data retrieved from GEM are almost of the same diachronic pace.

Year	Female/male Total early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity (TEA)		Female/male opportunity-D riven Total early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity		Fear of Failure rate		Perceived Capabilities		Cultural and social norms	
2020	0.80	0.90	n/a	n/a	41.2	31.0	64.00	47.6	4.05	n/a
2019	0.90	0.60	n/a	n/a	0	0	65.50	0	4.19	n/a
2018	0.80	0.50	0.90	1.00	35.1	29.7	55.60	45.8	4.30	2.65
2017	0.60	0.60	1.00	1.00	0	0	54.30	0	4.03	2.62
2016	0.71	0.52	0.99	1.04	35.2	35.1	55.00	38.3	4.07	2.59
2015	0.60	0.50	0.90	0.90	0	0	55.70	0	4.02	2.53
2014	0.68	0.61	0.93	0.94	33.4	36.3	53.30	37.5	3.75	2.65
2013	0.69	0.65	1.02	0.94	0	0	55.70	0	3.92	2.78
2012	0.69	0.50	n/a	n/a	33.3	41.0	55.90	37.4	4.12	2.74
2011	0.73	0.66	n/a	n/a	0	0	55.70	0	3.79	2.64
2010	0.90	0.50	n/a	n/a	29.4	42.3	59.50	36.2	3.85	2.61
2009	0.58	0.81	n/a	n/a	0	0	56.20	0	3.91	2.67
2008	0.70	0.84	n/a	n/a			55.70		3.87	2.52

201	0.60	n/a	n/a	n/a	29.7	39.9	48.30	36.4	4.47	n/a
4	0.58	0.45	n/a	n/a	0	0	51.20	0	4.54	2.37
201	0.63	0.61	n/a	n/a	31.1	38.6	52.10	37.7	4.31	2.49
3	0.90	0.42	n/a	n/a	0	0	54.20	0	4.59	2.64
201	0.52	0.47	n/a	n/a	32.3	41.9	54.00	37.1	4.52	2.39
2	0.64	0.49	n/a	n/a	0	0	57.10	0	3.98	2.61
201	0.68	0.44	n/a	n/a	31.2	42.0	60.60	37.1	n/a	2.91
1					0	0		0		
201					28.5	33.7		41.6		
0					0	0		0		
200					26.7	37.2		39.7		
9					0	0		0		
200					24.6	40.2		35.1		
8					0	0		0		
200					27.3	n/a		n/a		
7					0	34.3		39.0		
200					25.7	0		0		
6					0	40.2		40.6		
200					21.6	0		0		
5					0	30.1		35.8		
200					17.8	0		0		
4					0	32.8		38.2		
200					23.0	0		0		
3					0	37.1		35.2		
200					21.6	0		0		
2					0	41.8		30.1		
200					21.4	0		0		
1					0					

Table 1. Selected Entrepreneurial Behavior and attitude indicators, and Entrepreneurial Framework Conditions' rates of the Western category (Germany and the USA)

United States of America

Chart 1: Female/Male Total Entrepreneurship Activity and Female/Male Opportunity-Driven TEA of the Western category (USA and Germany)²

Diachronically speaking, there isn't a huge advancement because of the recurring peaks. For the USA there are three important peaks in 2004, 2010, and 2019 in which the ratio reaches 0.90. I conclude that the situation of women compared to men fluctuates (ups and downs) and the progress is not linear. However, in Germany, the values are ascending, the highest value is in 2020, and the lowest is in 2004. Although both of them are developed countries, the values never reach 1.00; therefore these environments never reached full equality between men and women in the entrepreneurship world.

As for the Female per Male Total early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity opportunity-driven ratio, the graph demonstrates there is somehow equality between men and women since in recent years the values reached 1.00 (percent

² OD refers to Opportunity-Driven

of women TEA, especially for Germany more than once. We can say that what drives men and women equally to entrepreneurship is the desire to have more income or because there aren't other job opportunities. We can conclude that the social and cultural environment, as well as the standards of living, push women and men towards the same entrepreneurship choices.

Chart 2: Fear of Failure³ and Perceived Capabilities⁴ of the Western category (USA and Germany)

The above graph shows the difference between the American and the European mentality toward entrepreneurship. In the USA everyone is chasing “the American dream”, the culture of the United States resides in business creation in all the fields (education, health, and technologies, e.g. Silicon Valley). However, the values are rising diachronically and that’s due to some economic setbacks that the USA has experienced lately, which created some Fear of Failure and doubts about one’s capabilities to face problematic phases like recession and inflation.

For Germany, the pace is somewhat stable, and both rates are somewhere in the middle. This could be explained by the different mentality in Europe.

³ FF refers to Fear of Failure

⁴ PC refers to Perceived Capabilities

European countries like Germany and France tend to unionize and have less privatization than the USA. The taxes are higher and the culture itself is not as encouraging as in the US. This leads us to the last part of this category.

Diagram1. Fear of Failure and Perceived Capabilities VS Female/Male TEA and Female/Male Opportunity-Driven TEA of the Western category.

Through the comparison of diagram 1, we notice that in the USA there is a negative correlation between the Female/Male Total early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity ratio and the Fear of Failure rate and there is a positive correlation

between the Female/Male Total early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity ratio and the Perceived capabilities rate. For example, from 2019 to 2020 the Female/Male TEA decreased from 0.90 to 0.80,

Perceived Capabilities also decreased from 66% to 64% and the Fear of Failure

rate increased from 35% to 41%.

Now observing Germany's curves in the diagram, we will come out with the same findings: there is a negative correlation between the

Female/Male Total early-stage

Entrepreneurial Activity ratio and the Fear of Failure rate while there is a positive correlation between the Female/Male Total early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity ratio and Perceived Capabilities rate. For example, from 2018 to 2020 the Female/Male Total early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity ratio increased from 0.50 to

0.90 at the same time the Perceived Capabilities rate increased from 38% to 48% and the Fear of Failure rate decreased from 35% to 31%

We can conclude that the more women are involved in the early-stage entrepreneurial activities the higher is the Perceived Capabilities rate as opposed to the Fear of Failure Rate. Thus, we can reject the idea saying men have higher self-efficacy than women in the Western category.

Chart 3. The extent to which social and cultural norms encourage new entrepreneurship activities in the Western category (Germany and the United States).

We can clearly see cultural differences between Germany and the USA. On the one hand, the USA has a culture that pushes and encourages both genders towards being involved in entrepreneurship. On the other hand, Germany's curve is stable: diachronically speaking the culture hasn't changed. Europe is a culture that values family time, retirement, and a healthier lifestyle compared to the USA. Many Europeans prefer being employees over holding a business and benefiting from government pensions and other public services. For example, Health and Education are free for most Europeans and unemployed people get help from the government. In exchange, it is well known that the taxes in Europe are high and not easy to dodge, the government is stronger than sole proprietorships and can directly or indirectly control business. This lifestyle is different from that in the United States where everyone seeks to get a higher income and focuses on the ways to generate it. Cultural and early education affect the entrepreneurial aspiration of the person along with the dependence on the government.

4.2. Second category: Arabic culture

The second category contains Morocco and Saudi Arabia. The reasons behind this choice of representation of Arabic culture are the following: First, Morocco is both an Arabic and African country, and, thus, it will be an excellent representation of this category. Second, Saudi Arabia is the center of Islamic culture and it has interesting diachronic findings. Third, both countries speak Arabic and have officially the same religion. They both politically belong to the Arabic League. The governing system is a monarchy and its laws are affected by Islamic laws, although Islam is not the only religion in Morocco (there are a significant number of Jews).

Year	female/male TEA		Female/male opportunity-Driven TEA		Perceived Capabilities		Fear of Failure		Cultural and social norms	
2020	0.5	1.00	n/a	n/a	63.40	86.40	38.7	51.6	2.32	-
2019	0	1.10	n/a	n/a	62.40	83.00	0	0	2.43	-
2018	0.5	0.60	1.10	0.80	29.50	83.40	42.5	41.8	2.31	3.25
2017	0	0.80	1.00	0.80	49.60	71.80	0	0	2.16	3.00
2016	0.5	0.75	1.05	1.03	56.10	70.70	64.2	43.6	2.47	2.72
2015	0	-	0.90	n/a	47.60	-	0	0	2.23	-
2010	0.4	0.50	n/a	n/a	-	69.30	52.9	34.4	-	3.14
2009	0	0.09	-	-	74.50	72.50	0	0	-	2.52

	0.6						32.9	39.4		
	7						0	0		
	0.5						41.1	-		
	0						0	39.0		
	-						-	0		
	0.5						28.7	48.9		
	9						0	0		

	Morocco
	Saudi Arabia

Table 2. Selected Entrepreneurial Behavior and attitude indicators

Chart 4: Female/Male Total Entrepreneurship Activity and Opportunity-Driven of the Arabic Category (Morocco and the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia) Entrepreneurial Framework Conditions' rates of the Arabic category

"Gender and business" were, is, and always will be a topic of debate in the Arabic world. However, in many countries, oppression against women isn't prevailing. Constatating the curve of Female/Male TEA, in Saudi Arabia there is huge progress. The curve is ascending from a very low value in 2009 to equality of ownership in 2020 between men and women. The involvement of women in entrepreneurship is even higher than men's in 2019. It is known in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia that the situation of women isn't delightful/the most fortunate. Women have much fewer rights than men. The apparent progress can be explained by the change in culture. The new King (Cheikh) has lessened a lot of burdens on women to encourage investment; therefore, the culture has been affected by foreigners who usually seek the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia for a higher paycheck than in their home countries. Women are more and more accepted, they are now allowed to drive and allowed, somehow, to choose their own dress code. And this facilitates women's day-to-day engagement in business. As for Morocco, the curve is stable as compared to the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia's curve. In 2020 the extent of involvement of women in entrepreneurship activities is half of men's. Women are driven towards entrepreneurship as much as men and for the same reason. There is a negative correlation between Female/ male TEA and Female/ Male Opportunity-driven TEA in both countries. In the early years, the few women who sought entrepreneurship didn't have many career options and the remuneration wasn't fair. When the situation of women progressed, the job opportunities became wider, and the reason why they pursue entrepreneurship is no longer for income purposes or because they are out of career options, but for personal ambitions and innovations.

Chart 5. Fear of Failure⁵ and Perceived Capabilities⁶ of the Arabic category (Morocco and the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia)

Observing the curves in chart 5, both curves of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia increase at the same pace, there is a clear positive correlation when one increases the other also increases. One possible explanation is that one doesn't cancel the other and both of them are increasing because people's involvement in entrepreneurship is increasing. Then by default, both percentages will increase. Differently, Morocco's curves are in opposite directions: There is a clear negative correlation between Perceived Capabilities and Fear of Failure for Morocco the higher the perceived capability rate the lower the Fear of Failure rate. Observing the curve, when the Perceived Capabilities rate decreases the Fear of Failure increases and vice versa. In detail, from 2009 to 2015 Perceived Capabilities decreased from 75% to 48%. In exchange, Fear of Failure increased from 29% to 41%. Again, from 2018 to 2020; Perceived Capabilities increased from 30% to 63% and Fear of Failure decreased from 64% to 39%. This could mean when people have less Fear of Failure people perceive themselves as more likely to succeed in entrepreneurship activities and have more trust in their capabilities.

⁵ FF: refers to Fear of Failure ⁶ PC: refers to Perceived capabilities

Diagram 2. Fear of Failure and Perceived Capabilities VS Female/Male TEA and Female/Male Opportunity-Driven TEA of the Arabic category.

As the diagram above indicates, there is a positive correlation between the increase in the perceived Capabilities and the increase in the involvement of women in entrepreneurship activities. This rejects the idea that women assess themselves as less capable compared to men however this doesn't necessarily prove the opposite.

We can say that Fear of Failure doesn't seem to be affected by women's involvement since the curve isn't increasing: For the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, it was actually high in 2009 when women were not much involved and slightly higher when women are equally involved. This point exactly can reject the idea that women have a higher Fear of Failure than men, however, this doesn't necessarily prove the opposite. From the observation, there is no correlation between women's involvement and Fear of Failure.

According to the GEM 2019-2020 global report, almost five out of ten of the adults in *the Middle East & Africa* regions assess themselves as having the suitable skills and knowledge to have successful entrepreneurship activities (although throughout these economies a third or more of adults seeing good opportunities would be discouraged by Fear of Failure.)

In Jordan, Egypt, Madagascar, and Morocco, a big percentage of people

(seven out of ten adults) agree that they rarely seize business opportunities. On the contrary, if we compare this situation to the Netherlands and Italy, we will find that only three out of ten adults have the same opinion.

Chart 6. The extent to which social and cultural norms encourage new entrepreneurship activities in the Arabic category (Morocco and Saudi Arabia)

The culture in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is more and more encouraging and it is positively correlated with increasing women's engagement in entrepreneurship activities due to their recent exposure to foreigners, their change of political rules after the death of their former Cheikh, and the new generation's mentality. Morocco's culture isn't as encouraging. Diachronically it has a steady pace. One explanation is that Morocco is highly affected by European culture, precisely France so it has similar rates, as discussed in the previous category. Morocco hasn't lived through any major political transitions like Saudi Arabia, and the culture's influence has remained the same.

4.3. Third category: Asian culture

The third category contains China and South Korea. The reasons behind this choice of representation of Asian culture are the following: Both of these countries are of Asian origins and are part of the Asian continent. Korea has adopted some aspects of Chinese culture like their customs and the Confucian philosophy since it is a neighboring country.

year	Female/male TEA		Female/male opportunity-Driven TEA		Perceived Capabilities		Fear of Failure rate		Cultural and social norms	
2020	0.70	0.8	n/a	n/a	53.00	67.4	13.80	44.7	-	-
2019	0.60	0	n/a	1.00	51.70	0	7.10	0	-	3.62
2018	0.70	0.8	1.00	1.10	49.70	24.2	32.80	41.7	3.07	3.23
2017	0.70	0	1.00	0.95	45.70	0	32.20	0	2.99	3.47
2016	0.66	0.9	0.99	1.10	45.10	27.2	31.50	41.5	2.97	2.98
2015	0.70	0	1.00	0.88	14.40	0	27.40	0	2.93	2.89
2013	0.40	0.7	1.06	0.82	12.70	29.8	28.10	49.1	3.09	3.00
2012	0.21	3	n/a	n/a	12.50	0	26.90	0	3.08	2.97
2011	0.32	0.7	n/a	n/a	11.20	27.4	26.70	40.0	3.00	-
2010	0.20	0	n/a	n/a	13.00	0	29.00	0	3.02	3.35
2009	0.33		n/a	n/a	12.80		52.80		3.08	-

2008	0.34	0.8	n/a	n/a	14.80	33.0	30.10	39.5	3.53	-
2007	-	4	n/a	n/a	-	0	-	0	-	3.07
2006	-	0.7	n/a	n/a	-	36.3	-	34.3	-	-
2005	-	7	-	n/a	-	0	-	0	-	2.94
2004	-	0.7	-	n/a	-	37.6	-	35.8	-	4.58
2003	-	5	-	-	-	0	-	0	-	2.97
2002	0.42	0.8	-	-	14.70	43.9	31.40	35.6	3.04	3.05
2001	0.42	7	-	-	12.20	0	28.60	0	3.11	
		0.8				42.3		32.0		
		0				0		0		
		0.7				35.2		32.1		
		8				0		0		
		-				-		-		
		0.7				38.9		31.0		
		0				0		0		
		0.8				36.4		31.7		
		9				0		0		
		0.7				22.6		13.9		
		4				0		0		
		-				-		-		
		-				37.5		28.3		
		0.8				0		0		
		1				35.9		36.9		
		0.7				0		0		
		6				-		-		
		-								

Chart 7. Female/Male Total Entrepreneurship and Opportunity-Driven 7 Total Entrepreneurship Activities of the Asian category (South Korea and China)

	South Korea
	China

On one hand, the involvement of women in China in the early-stage entrepreneurial activities (Female/Male TEA) is higher than in Korea, which is explained by the Country having an economy based on business. China is known for hard workers in the import-export field. However, there isn't any apparent progress over the years. The curve is somewhat stable. For example, in 2007 the ratio was 0.70 and in 2016 it was also 0.70. The ratios are slightly fluctuating around the same values which means there isn't much change. On the other hand, there is visible progress diachronically from 2010 to 2013: the ratio doubled from 0.20 to 0.40; after that, it has been increasing. Still, for both countries, the ratio of female/male TEA never reaches 1 which means the involvement of women in the early stage of entrepreneurial activities has never been equal to men's.

When we observe the curve for Female/Male Opportunity-Driven TEA Ratio it's vice versa, the curve of South Korea is steady and of China is increasing. The percentage of females involved in TEA who firstly claim to be driven by opportunity as opposed to finding no other option for work and secondly who indicate the main driver for being involved in the opportunity is to be independent or to increase their income, rather than just maintaining their income are is mostly equal to their men counterparts' percentage for both countries and sometimes the percentage of females is higher (in 2013 for South Korea; in 2016 and 2018 for China). This is because job demand is higher for men and women are usually paid less, especially by offshore companies that go specifically to China (mostly) for this reason.

⁷ OD refers to Opportunity-Drive

⁸ Offshore refers to any (business) activity that takes place outside an entity's home base (source: investpedia.com)

Chart 8: Percentage of Fear of Failure⁹ and Perceived Capabilities¹⁰ of the Asian category (South Korea and China)

Observing chart 8 Fear of Failure rate and Perceived Capabilities rate have a negative correlation because the curves go in the opposite ways for example in 2009 the Perceived Capabilities rate was 13% while Fear of Failure is at its highest at 53%, while in 2019 Perceived Capabilities rate is 52% while Fear of failure rate was at its lowest of 7%. As opposed to the Fear of Failure rate, the Perceived Capabilities rate is increasing with time, especially after 2015 (see table 2). There is a visible slope between 2015 and 2016 (see chart 8.) when the rate increased from 14% to 45%.

As for China, the Fear of Failure rate and Perceived Capabilities are positively correlated; they increase and decrease almost at the same time. For example, from 2005 to 2006 Perceived Capabilities rate increased from 23% to 36% and the Fear of failure rate increased from 14% to 32%. Unfortunately, I haven't found

enough data explaining this correlation.

⁹ FF refers to Fear of Failure

¹⁰ PC refers to Perceived Capabilities

Diagram 3. Fear of Failure and Perceived Capabilities VS Female/Male TEA and Female/Male Opportunity-Driven TEA of the Asian Category.

Focusing on South Korea, we can see a visible positive correlation between the Female/ male Total early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity rate and Perceived Capabilities Rate. The increase of involvement of women in the early stage of entrepreneurial activities coincides with or is followed by the increase in the percentage of people who think that they have the necessary skills to start a business. We can conclude that contrary to what is typical, women assess themselves positively more than men and this is backed up by the negative correlation between the Female/ male Total early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity rate and the Fear of Failure rate: when the Fear of Failure rate is at its highest by 53% in 2009 there is fewer women’s involvement in the entrepreneurship activities, the Female% Male TEA ratio is at 0.33 in 2009 and in 2019 the ratio almost doubled, becoming at 0.66. This coincides with the Fear of failure of 7% (see table 3). There is enough evidence to reject the idea that men have higher self-efficacy than women in South Korea however there isn’t enough evidence to prove the contrary.

Chart 9. The extent to which social and cultural norms encourage new entrepreneurship activities in the Asian category (China and South Korea)

South Korea's curve is almost stable but China's curve is fluctuating with a peak in 2004. In 2005, fear of failure reached the lowest percentage. According to the GEM global report of the year 2005, China is among the countries with the highest rate of established business owners at about 13%. And this follows the year of the cultural peak (2004) in which the social and cultural norms encouraged new entrepreneurship activities.

5. Comparative analysis

In this section, I will try to make a global comparison emphasizing the three categories under investigation. I am going to apply some of Hofstede's Dimensions to explain some correlations. Professor Geert Hofstede created the 6 Dimensions model of the national culture which are

- Power Distance Index (PDI)
- Individualism versus Collectivism (IDV)
- Masculinity versus Femininity (MAS)
- Uncertainty Avoidance Index (UAI)
- Long Term Orientation versus Short Term Normative Orientation (LTO)
- Indulgence versus Restraint (IVR)

5.1. Gender

According to Global Entrepreneurship Monitor's global report for 2019 and 2020, the United Arab Emirates has the highest rate of Support for women entrepreneurs at 7.9, then the second-highest is in Europe in Lithuania at 7.0 and the third-highest rate is in India at 5.1. Although the United Arab Emirates has the highest rate, it is not representative of the middle east, as the support for women entrepreneurs is the lowest in Israel at 3.5, in Turkey at 3.2, and in Iran at 2.5. The following chart contains the three categories (Western, Arabic, and Asian). The upwards bars represent Female/Male Total early-stage Entrepreneurship Activity and the downwards bars are for Female/Male Opportunity-Driven Total early-stage Entrepreneurship Activity for the equivalent years. The categories are separated by the blue line from left to right as follows: Western, Arabic, and Asian cultures.

Female/ Male TEA and Female/Male Opportunity Driven TEA -Global comparison

Chart 10. Female/Male TEA and Female/Male Opportunity-Driven TEA- A comparison between Asian, Arabic, and Western cultures.

Observing Chart 10, Western Culture’s Female/ Male Total early-stage Entrepreneurship activity ratio is not developing at a particular pace, we can say that it is almost stable that there isn’t much of a difference between the past and the future in women’s involvement in entrepreneurship. The bars of the United States presented in gray create a general image that is very close to the one of China’s presented in light blue: both countries have almost the same progress in women’s involvement although they have different Cultures and different business approaches, they have the same goal, that is a monopoly of the market. According to Hofstede’s dimensions, China has a high ranking (at 80) in Power distance, the culture accepts inequalities among people, and it is a collectivist culture with a score of 20

(<https://www.hofstede-insights.com/country-comparison/china/>) indicating that the Chinese put business before personal relationships. China is also a masculine society and success-oriented. The Chinese people prioritize work over personal time. In comparison, the United States' culture does not have a high tolerance for inequalities like in China. If we combine this with the fact that the USA is an individualistic society, we can emphasize the evidence that the culture and government believe that liberty and justice are for everyone. In addition, as previously mentioned, compared to Germany, the Americans do not rely on authorities, they focus on themselves and their direct family only. The closeness of shape of these two countries can be explained by how close their scores are on the scale of Hofstede's masculinity dimension (according to Hofstede's insight).

Both South Korean and the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia bars (which are illustrated in yellow) create a shape skewed to the left. There is apparent progress for both cultures. The only difference is that the progress of Saudi Arabia's Female/Male TEA ratio is more acute diachronically. Between the years 2009 and 2020, there was a huge difference from barely having women's involvement in early-stage entrepreneurship activity to having even more involvement than men. However, the progress in South Korea is smoother. South Korea has an intermediate hierarchy system, the power distance score (according to Hofstede's insight) is fairly close to Saudi Arabia's, the same thing as the masculinity score. Both of these countries are considered to have feminine societies. The fast increase of the Female / Male TEA in Saudi Arabia compared to the steady and slow increase of the Female/Male TEA in South Korea is due to the new mentality of taking risks and approaching new opportunities: the higher the risk the higher the profit. Korean people do not care about money as much as they care about personal growth and taking measured steps. The score of long-term orientation is very close to the USA's.

Morocco's Female/Male TEA ratio is almost stable diachronically and we can conclude that, especially in the last years, women's involvement was low, and

half of the men's involvement in early-stage entrepreneurship activity.

The Moroccan society is a normative one according to the long-term orientation, among these categories, it has the lowest score so far. The culture is still attached to traditions and the ways of the past; this could be an explanation of why male's involvement in early-stage entrepreneurship activity is double in comparison to that of women and why the progress is stable and not increasing but as a matter of fact, the decreasing shape of the yellow bars is a little bit skewed to the right. This comes as no surprise, especially because Hofstede's scores are recent.

According to the GEM's 2019/2020 global report, entrepreneurial activities that work towards gender equality and local incomes are high in Saudi Arabia, Qatar which is another Arabic country, Madagascar and Brazil. However, it is low in Pakistan, Japan, North Macedonia, and Norway which makes these cultures a distinctive group. The statistics of these findings suggest that countries like Saudi Arabia have a high potential for new businesses nowadays and more importantly increased empowerment not only for the nation but for minorities within the nation.

Asian Culture has higher collectivism than Arabic culture. The Western culture is considered to have an individualistic society that could explain the change in traditional business and the progress of female/male ratio participation. There isn't a huge difference between categories to exploit when it comes to Female/Male opportunity-driven early-stage Entrepreneurship Activity other than to back up the previous explanation. Although when I analyzed the graph in Global Entrepreneurship Monitor 2019/2020 Global Report on page 48, In general, those who engage in the Total early-stage Entrepreneurship Activity, and somewhat strongly agree with the motive of making a difference in the world thus pursuing entrepreneurship, are mostly Women. The percentage of women is higher than the percentage of men. Moreover, the percentage of those women in Germany is higher than in the United States. Keeping our category classification in mind, Arabic culture has a surprisingly small percentage of men as opposed to the Western culture. Asian cultures have both small percentages; the Republic of

Korea's for men and China's for women. These results entitle us to say that changing the world is not the main focus of Asian culture in terms of entering entrepreneurship.

5.2. Self-Efficacy

According to the 20019-2020 global report of Global Entrepreneurship Monitor, the lowest percentage of adults who agree that they see good business opportunities but don't pursue them out of fear of failure was from South Korea with 7% In 2019. The next lowest percentages are from three European countries: Switzerland, the Netherlands, and Italy.

Fear of Failure and Perceived Capabilities -Global comparison

Chart 11: Fear of Failure and Perceived capabilities rates – a comparison between

Asian, Arabic, and western culture.

The USA has the highest Fear Failure rate, especially in 2020 and 2012, and Germany in 2011 and 2012. According to Hofstede's dimensions, the USA has a high masculinity level. Typical American behavior is to always seek success and try to be the best. Since Childhood kids in school try to win in sports competitions, for example, the competition mentality grows with the person and creates the urge to compete within his career and this behavior is very up-front. However, this competitive mindset doesn't move as a unified culture but at an individual level, because people are expected to rely on themselves. The value shared by the whole culture is to thrive and be the best at what they do because the winner gets everything in the end. For this reason, we notice privatization in the monopoly of business in the USA whereas in Europe Monopoly is usually owned by the government. This mentality comes from the ambitious culture of American society where people are able to do anything. That's why most Americans are workaholics, increasing in rank at work is their objective in life and this is a common point with the German culture, although there are some differences. To move vertically in society and in entrepreneurship, the promotions are based on merit. Americans oppose the separation of class because they believe anyone can reach the top and become rich and a very famous entrepreneur. Speaking of entrepreneurship, American society has a great tolerance for new ideas. People believe in themselves and face risks to pursue innovation and they accept different opinions in the name of freedom of expression and the American premise of "justice and liberty for all". But we need to mention the effect of 9/11 that created fear of being different and created a

different set of fear of failure among Americans of different ethnicity pursuing entrepreneurship. Uncertainty avoidance scores can explain the fluctuations of

Fear of Failure and Perceived Capabilities rates, USA's score rests below average. The American culture always seeks immediate results, they evaluate their business on a short-term basis, through which we can conclude that they have anxiety about long-term risks and that's what increased their fear of failure.

In the same category, the Germans believe in self-actualization, which subjectively explains the stability of the Perceived capabilities rate over the years. Germany is considered to have a quite high uncertainty avoidance rate (score of 65). Germany's culture values truth, they tell it no matter how harsh it is. This affects the Fear of Failure rate in Germany because any innovation would be exposed to severe evaluation. To maintain high uncertainty avoidance, Germans rely on expertise the most.

Saudi Arabia has the highest Perceived Capabilities rate, especially in recent years - 86% in 2020. The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia has a collectivistic society, its culture relies on family ties and the group's support, this ongoing support could boost self-confidence in taking risk while pursuing entrepreneurship, therefore, affecting self-efficacy positively. Saudi society is contained by rules thus it prefers uncertainty avoidance and innovation is somehow resisted contrary to the USA. Morocco is also a collectivistic society, the culture is not very welcoming of untraditional behavior and this is why compared to the other categories, the Arabic category, in general, has a high Fear of Failure rate, Morocco precisely has a culture that is suspicious about innovative ideas, which make by default the Arabic category (both countries) representative of normative society.

Observing the shape of the bars of the Asian category, this category has the lowest perceived capability rates. This can be explained by some characteristics of Asian society. South Korea has the lowest Perceived capabilities rate precisely before 2015. South Korea is one of the most uncertain countries in the world according to the fourth of Hofstede's dimensions with a high score of 85, South Koreans are not so threatened by uncertainty and ambiguity. As a conservative society, Koreans are punctual and respect the rules. Besides, with 100 as a high score in Uncertainty Avoidance, South Korea is the most pragmatic among the selected countries, Korean entrepreneurs always have long-term plans. The fact that South Korea's score was high (70 in 2003) but reached 100 (<https://www.hofstede-insights.com/country-comparison/south-korea/>), which is one of the highest scores in the world, can explain the drop in the Fear of Failure rate in recent years. Koreans think about the next generation while conducting business contrary to the USA's approach to entrepreneurship, where entrepreneurs plan in the short term. Another explanation is that Koreans are very careful, they believe in steady growth rather than taking risks. Usually, Koreans' behaviors are controlled by pessimism which can explain the low Perceived Capabilities rate. China has a collectivist society, moving vertically in a career could rely on family ties, and promotion acts upon preferential treatment, around 80% (<https://www.hofstede-insights.com/country-comparison/china/>) of the businesses are family-owned. The well-being of the group, in China, comes before the well-being of the individual. Although it belongs to the same Asian group, unlike South Korea China has a low uncertainty avoidance score: the Chinese people respect the rules but they are pragmatic to make these rules flexible according to the situation. Chinese people in general have no aspirations beyond their rank. Applying the uncertainty avoidance dimension, China is a Restrained society as can be seen in its low score of 24 on this dimension.

The Chinese tend toward cynicism and pessimism. There is a certain stability in the flow of the rates across the years. The shape created by the bars is very similar to the one of the USA's excluding the peak years. Chinese entrepreneurs have a strong ability to save and invest, their businesses and services have become very popular in recent years, and their adaptability to the COVID-19 situation, and the use of technology to overcome the crisis have been outstanding. This proves their ability to fight ambiguity and unknown threats which explains the visible increase in the Perceived Capabilities rate in 2020; from 24% in 2019 to 67% in 2020. While the Coronavirus ended many startups, the Chinese people saw opportunity and confidence in their ability to provide innovative services and products adaptable to the situation.

5.3. Cultural and Social Norms

According to the recent information published on the website of the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor, the countries that have a highly sufficient extent to which social and cultural norms encourage or allow entrepreneurial methods

and activities are mostly placed in North America with rates around 5. The global report for 2019 and 2020 identified Israel to have the highest rate of 7.94 followed by Lithuania (6.15) Jamaica (5.84), and Japan to have the lowest rate of 3.63 followed by Croatia (2.96) Sudan (3.40)

CHART 13 : The extent to which social and cultural norms encourage new entrepreneurship activities of all the three categories under investigation (Line Graph)

Chart14. The extent to which social and cultural norms encourage new entrepreneurship activities of all the three categories under investigation (Bar Graph)

As we can see in Chart13, the USA's line represented in dark blue is above all the lines, while the rest of the countries' lines reside around the same range and this shows the distinctive culture of the USA to encourage entrepreneurship. Moreover, in Chart14 if we take a look at each category, we will find that every two countries have close rates except for the western category, there is a gap between the United States and Germany's cultural rates. This graph also shows us the perseverance of this culture across the years since the rate remained high and we can see clear stability.

The United States is considered an indulgent society according to the last Dimension of Hofstede's 6-D model. The Americans are still prudish despite the evolution of televangelists. It's one of the few countries where ties with religion have increased. The contrast in American society comes from the objective to work hard to make as much money as possible in order to live the best life and have the best time, for this they don't neglect their leisure time, in other words, the "have it all" mentality is a characteristic trait of the Americans. This is one of the reasons behind the increased drug use. People, even those of high rank, abuse the use of drugs to stay sharp. But on the other hand, the system is trying to fight the use of drugs. Self et al. (2011), compared the United States and Korea quoting Hofstede (2003) (2011: 11). They pointed out that in general, the United States' business ethics are influenced by protestant religion whereas Korea's cultural and social norms are highly influenced by Confucianism. This takes us to the Asian Category. The Chinese people, unlike the Americans, do not give importance to leisure time. Chinese society falls among the restraint societies.

Not only do the Chinese lack ambition as compared to the Americans, but they are also restrained by social norms. However, the extent of encouragement of the Chinese social norms comes from the society is a pragmatic one. The Chinese are known to be very perseverant and patient to achieve excellence. This education is rooted in Chinese culture and therefore affects entrepreneurship intentions. As a matter of fact, this exactly applies to Korean society, too. South Korea's score of indulgence of 29 is almost as low as China's score of 24. On Chart14, in 2016, the bars show how similar the social norms of these two countries are. As previously discussed, South Korea is also a very pragmatic society if not the most pragmatic. Koreans are guided by good examples in their society. In the entrepreneurial world, success stories are the best motivators.

At last, I consider the Arabic category to have the least encouraging culture towards entrepreneurship activities, among the three categories. And this emerges from my deeper insight on Morocco, which, compared to the rest of the investigated countries, has the lowest of the total rates. Morocco, like the Asian cultures, has a restrained society ruled by traditions, and going out of these traditions is considered to be wrong. This precise idea is backed by the fact that Hofstede labeled Moroccan society as normative, and this is where it clearly differs from Asian culture. Moroccan culture focuses on the present and does not engage in plans for the future. As for Saudi Arabia, it is the most restrained country on our list, in the 6-D model of Hofstede, Saudi Arabia scored only 14 in indulgence (<https://www.hofstede-insights.com/country-comparison/saudi-arabia/>).

Similarly, to Morocco Saudi Arabia has a normative society, as we observe from the soft pink bars in Chart14, Saudi Arabia prospers to become like the Emirates in terms of entrepreneurial achievements, so Saudi Arabia is encouraging its citizens and foreigners to adhere to the entrepreneurship world on its land. Its society is culturally changing and becoming more tolerant of innovative ideas, but it is not yet clear to what extent...

Conclusion

The numbers suggest how these social and cultural foundations for entrepreneurship vary by global region and the economy's income level. Social attitudes, as well as culture, affect entrepreneurship and vice versa.

The idea is to highlight the interaction of an individual's Perceived Capabilities and gender within a specific cultural context. In general, individuals' attitudes and perceptions set within social and cultural contexts support or constrain entrepreneurship activities; therefore, entrepreneurial activity is determined by both social values and individual attributes, it is about how people perceive the cultural environment as enabling or constraining.

The USA has the highest ratio of cultural and social norms; we can consider the Western culture to be more encouraging and enabling of entrepreneurship activities. Thus, we accept hypothesis 1.

Many causes could be the reason behind the gender gap in TEA and Opportunity-Driven TEA, among which we can enumerate: political changes, cultural stability and instability, stereotypes, and business' perceived ideas.

We can say that there is a relatively small gap between Western and Eastern cultures depending on the years. In the early years, the gender gap was small in the Western culture and big in Asian culture. However, in recent years, the gender gap in Western culture remains, and the Arabic culture is progressing towards equality. Therefore, we can neither accept nor reject hypothesis 2; further research is needed.

In the Western category, there is a negative correlation between the Female/Male Total early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity ratio and the Fear of Failure rate, while there is a positive correlation between the Female/Male Total

early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity ratio and Perceived Capabilities rate. In the USA there is a negative correlation between the Female/Male Total early-stage

Entrepreneurial Activity ratio and the Fear of Failure rate and there is a positive correlation between the Female/Male Total early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity ratio and the Perceived capabilities rate. We can reject the idea that men have higher self-efficacy than women in the Western category.

Within the Arabic category, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia has a collectivistic society; its culture relies on family ties and the group's support. This ongoing support could boost self-confidence in taking risks while pursuing entrepreneurship, therefore, affecting self-efficacy positively. The culture of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is more and more encouraging and it is positively correlated with the increasing women's engagement in entrepreneurship activities. Furthermore, in the Arabic category, there is a positive correlation between the increase in the Perceived Capabilities and the increase in the involvement of women in entrepreneurship activities. This rejects the idea that women assess themselves as less capable compared to men; however, this doesn't necessarily prove the opposite. There is no correlation between women's involvement in entrepreneurship and Fear of Failure. There is a clear negative correlation between Perceived Capabilities and Fear of Failure for Morocco: the higher the Perceived Capability rate, the lower the Fear of Failure rate.

In the Asian category, China's Fear of Failure rate and Perceived Capabilities are positively correlated. In South Korea, there is a positive correlation between the Female/ male Total early-stage Entrepreneurial Activity rate and the Perceived Capabilities Rate. In conclusion, we accept hypothesis 3.

6. Implication

My study is not only constructed upon previous entrepreneurship research but also explored uninvestigated parts related to this domain. The cross-cultural scope of the study creates a foundation for future research exploring other nations and investigating other influencing factors. Since it is built on official data from the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor, I hope my paper will make a valuable contribution to international entrepreneurship research and to the global consortium itself.

Cross-cultural comparative studies of gender, self-efficacy, and social norms are quite rare and there is a big demand in this area. Moreover, my research methodology and findings can be used by other researchers to investigate other correlations.

7. Limitations

Because my study has some flaws, I am explaining the limitations and offering directions. One important limitation of this study is the primary method of research which utilized one source of data: the global consortium GEM operating only with quantitative information. Although I applied Hofstede's dimensions of cultures to provide explanations. It would have been useful to use another source of data, as well. Mainly, qualitative data would have been of great value to this study. For example, interviewing some experts on the matter... Another limitation that may hinder the impact of my findings is the limited number of countries within each cultural category. To have deeper credible conclusions, it is advisable to explore more countries' statistics. One last limitation is that GEM did not cover all the years for some developing countries since it is a quite recent database. It might have been challenging to make a comparative analysis diachronically.

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